

Studying the Dropout Status of Ethnic Minority Students: The Case of Vietnam

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Abstract:

The article has synthesized the theory of studying dropout behavior of ethnic minority students. By the method of synthesizing secondary materials, the paper analyzed the dropout status of minority students in Vietnam, analyzing the causes of drop-outs of minority students. Since then, we have combined research results with a theoretical basis to provide solutions to reduce the dropout rate of ethnic minority students in Vietnam. The paper will be better if a combination of quantitative research data on factors influencing students' intention to drop out of Vietnam

Keywords: Dropouts of students, Vietnam, ethnic minorities

1. Introduction

Children are the future of a nation and children need to enjoy the best conditions to develop physical and intellectual perfection. One of the ways for children to complete their personality is through education. Basic education of our country is divided into 3 levels of education to help children access to knowledge at each level, different levels in accordance with the ability to receive and analyze information, corresponding to the process of developing the mind child's physiology. The goal of general education is to help students develop morally, intellectually, physically, aesthetically and basic skills in order to shape the personality of the Vietnamese Socialist people, building citizenship and responsibility.

In order for an economy to develop sustainably, the human factor always plays a decisive role. Therefore, not only Vietnam but also all countries in the world consider education as the top national policy. Along with the above trend, Vietnam always creates all conditions to improve people's intellectual standards, train human resources, foster talents for the country and improve the professional and technical qualifications of workers, in order to better meet the needs for the demand of industrialization and modernization of the country. Education plays an important role, but recently, public opinion is "hot" because of the dropout information. The situation of mass dropout students is increasing in localities. Especially, the majority of ethnic minority students in mountainous areas. It can be seen that overcoming the current dropout of students in general and ethnic minority students talking is a very pressing issue and requires the attention of many components in the society.

2. Literature review and theories

Research of UNICEF (2010) shows that "While enrollment rates are improving, the dropout is one of the problems that almost all developing countries face. This has not only a direct impact on the outcome of universal primary education but also a waste of resources and an increase in illiterate people. In large population countries, enrollment rates are high. At the same time, the dropout rate in these countries is also high. Education policy relates to a country's policy of economic development and population policy. Most countries are confronted with a dropout of students in various stages, which has become a topic for many researchers to find practical solutions for the nation's education sector the part that promotes equality in all areas.

Okumu, Ibrahim M., Naka jo, Alex and Isoke, Doren (2008) analyzed the socio-economic factors that led to the decision to drop out of primary school students in Uganda. Researchers have established a logistics model for analyzing national data in 2004, and this analysis model has analyzed in cohorts for the age of rural and urban students, by gender. count. The analysis results show that variables such as gender, the total amount paid for school fees and the gender of the household head do not affect the dropout rate of primary school students. But

variables such as family size, parental education, the type of economic activity of household members, especially in rural areas, have important implications for opportunities. continue learning or dropout rates of students. Even that, Robert Balfanz and Nettie Legters (2004) pointed out that there are regions and regions with high dropout rates that are often weak schools, with many ethnic minority students and learning outcomes. School assignments are often poor in subjects such as math, literature ... In addition, these schools are often those located in areas where the surrounding community has a high rate of unemployment, crime, and education problem is not high.

Dang Thi Hai Tho (2010) has pointed out the causes of family problems such as difficult economy, early labor, unhappy families, families without traditional learning and family deficiencies, many babies. The reasons that originated from the school were that the education program was not practical; the quality of teaching and teaching methods was unattractive, less interested, teachers had problems; the language was a barrier. Besides, the author has pointed out the causes from society, from the young ones themselves, other impact factors.

Social work in the field has been mentioned a lot in recent years in order to contribute to solving outstanding problems in education. In fact, we have seen, investment in education is sustainable development. Today's investment achievements are prosperous of the society tomorrow, which is a solid development when the next good class of the future can shoulder the tasks of the previous generation of construction. But education in the present age of the country faces numerous challenges. There were a few schools in Ho Chi Minh City applying for social work in school, but for a short time, the projects were cut or not continued. Recently, when the public opinion press has talked a lot about the situations that occur in the school environment, more or less because children are "polluted" from their own living environment so that society gradually regains awareness. the educational process of each family, of the whole education system of the whole country in which many opinions of prestigious people believe that our country's education is more about teaching words than teaching people and children lacking skills. the vital skills needed in integration, so the children lack the ability to communicate, the skills to cope with the crisis occur or when confronted with a problem that is too much for the child to endure, causing the child to be depressed, stressed and causing unwanted behaviors, including the problem of dropping out of school, is also a sign of behavior If the system of standard behavior to cope with difficulties in learning from subjective or objective.

The concept of "Ethnic Minorities," clarified in Article 5, Decree No. 05 / NDCP on the Ethnic Minority Work of the Government issued on January 14, 2011, stipulates: "Ethnic minorities are ethnic groups. there is a smaller population than the majority in the territory of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam "and" the majority of the population is a nation with a population of over 50% of the total population of the country, according to National Census "The concept of" Minority group "is used to refer to groups of people who have some differences in the social community. They may be different from the majority group in terms of language and culture. Differences in awareness and religion, economic circumstances, living conditions, and income ... accompanied by differences in the behavior of the community to themselves.

System theory was developed in the 1930s and 1940s initiated by biologist Ludvig Von Bertalanffy. The system theory covers all fields (informatics, biology, economics, sociology) a system is defined as a complex whole of certain factors that affect other factors and also impact on the whole system. A system can consist of many sub-systems and is part of a large system. There are closed systems, not exchanging with surrounding systems. "The system is a whole, maintaining existence with the interaction between the components that make it." Elements of a system often participate in many other systems, which requires each element to perform well the role of each system in which it plays. The system approach is not completely synonymous with the method of system analysis because, in addition to the method (still being developed and perfected), access to the system also mentioned the problem of system theory as well as this theoretical application direction in practice.

Abraham Maslow's theory of needs: his theory to explain how certain human needs need to be met in order for an individual to lead a healthy and useful life both physically and mentally. His theory helps our understanding

of human needs by identifying a hierarchy of needs. He brought different types of human needs, based on its demands and their preceding generation order, to refer to the five types of arrangements into a hierarchy of low to high human needs.

3. The dropout status of students

According to statistics of the school year 2017 - 2018, the whole country has 125,000 dropouts at the middle school level (secondary school) and high school (high school). In recent years, with special support from the Party, the State and the various levels and departments, the dropout rate has decreased in proportion, but the number is still increasing and really worth "alarming." As of December 2017, the number of secondary school dropouts is 65,735 students (accounting for 1.1% of the number of students at the same level) and in high school students is 51,102 students (accounting for 1.66%). Provinces with a high number of dropouts are Yen Bai with 18,000 students, Ha Giang with nearly 7,000 students. In particular, the majority of students drop out of school concentrated at the secondary level, and it is really numbers that startle us.

The dropout rate of students has come to an alarming level; it not only exists in remote areas, especially difficult areas but also in provinces with developed economies. Since the previous school years, the education and training sector has had many solutions to prevent the dropout of students in general and lower secondary students in particular, but the efficiency is not high.

4. Causes of dropping out of school

Improving the quality of education is an urgent need for the era and is the development target of each country. For Vietnam, education is always considered a top national policy. Therefore, before the current dropout situation of students requires the relevant departments and organizations to find ways to prevent and overcome. However, it is necessary first to understand and determine the cause of this situation. Through the process of research and information collection, our team found that there are some main reasons for the dropout status of secondary school students as follows:

Firstly, due to difficult family economic conditions, parents are not eligible for their children to go to school to force them to drop out of school. Partly because parents have to take care of their livelihoods, do not have time to care and remind them to study and lead to lazy learning, do not want to go to class. In case of a difficult family situation, the children have to drop out of school to stay at the women's side or work early to cover the parents. However, this is not an absolute cause because there are difficult families, but their children still go to school and still study very well, it also depends on the attitude of parents and their personality. This explains why there are families with conditions for children to go to school even rich, but their children still do not go to class but just like to go out.

Secondly, because the family moved and worked away from home, their study was not guaranteed. This is a cause that occurs mainly in the provinces of the countryside or in the rural areas because the economic conditions here are difficult, so parents have to relocate. Meanwhile, children are still young, forcing their parents to let their children follow, which greatly affects their learning. Many households, after moving, also find ways to send their children to another school, but they still drop out of school for many reasons: failing to get used to the new environment, not keeping up with friends due to scattered learning. in the process of family relocation.... But there are also many families due to difficult economic circumstances and many other reasons, so they forced their children to drop out of school: they do not have a household registration book, they do not have personal papers (birth certificate), lose school records.

Thirdly, because the advanced curriculum in knowledge and textbooks is not suitable for many places, it leads to the situation of poor students, discouragement and drops out of school. The education program of the Ministry of Education for junior high school students who are still "heavy" and not suitable for students in mountainous areas. The children did not keep up with the program, did not absorb the lesson, leading to poor

learning, boredom and not wanting to go to school. Many ethnic students are not yet proficient in speaking Kinh, so it is very slow to acquire lessons, sometimes do not understand, making students feel reluctant to learn.

Fourthly, in some high schools, the school is still too difficult to meet the quality of teaching, not to promote their learning spirit. Many lower secondary schools in the highlands are very poor (sluggish schools, rotten tables, and chairs ...), teaching and learning conditions, especially the equipment for the reception of lectures (practical tools) are hardly available. Should lead to feeling bored and watching learning as a burden, so they don't want to go to class. In addition, there is a reason that the school is too far away, they have to travel long distances to go to class (sometimes go to 1-2 hours), especially if the weather conditions are bad for a while. long (storms, floods, surges ...), they are forced to leave school.

Fifth, because they themselves do not have the will to rise in learning, are afraid of difficulty, play ... Students do not want to study for many reasons but do not get the attention of families, so they often drop out to hang out or play games. Besides, the enticing of friends made them no longer interested in learning, just playing all day and gradually becoming habits. On the other hand, their psychology is in the ages of 12 to 16, this is the most volatile age, if there is a good rectification measure, they will go in a positive direction and vice versa they will become damaged.

5. Solution

Firstly, it is necessary to have a campaign "Say no to the phenomenon of dropout students due to difficult circumstances," unable to let children because of poverty but illiterate. Need to review priority policies, support poor students, supplement new incentives, have solutions to mobilize financial resources for poor students, practice savings to save money for poor students, push strong philanthropy in schools, mobilizing wealthy students to help you poor. Currently, poor students only get ½ tuition reduction and other contributions are equal as other students, the press also mentioned a lot about the phenomenon of "collecting and collecting money" in schools, one of the reasons. The poor students have to drop out of school. Many schools not only have no measures to help poor students but also "create" the revenues to "drain" students. It is necessary to have policies for poor families to borrow money for their children to go to high school, as well as have regulations on "punishment" of schools and localities so that students have to drop out of school because of poverty. For disadvantaged localities, it is necessary to survey and survey and ask the state for funding support.

Secondly, the school needs to coordinate with the police offices of communes, wards, and mass organizations: The Women's Union, Youth Union, the Management Board of the residential group to each family of pupils who drop out or intend to give up. Learn to encourage and motivate themselves and their families so that they can return to school. This is also the solution that we have consulted from the teachers at the secondary schools that we surveyed. With the attention of the school, the neighborhood group or the police agencies, mass organizations, as well as their families, will have the best decisions to have a good future, and at the same time, they will see how the impact of dropout affects my future in the future. From there they have a new way of thinking, thinking and deciding to return to school.

Third, to limit students to drop out, there should be solutions from all levels and departments, in which the education and training sector plays an important role. The basic solution to combat dropout for high school students is to divide students after junior high school. Encouraging a part of students including those who are not eligible to finish high school to go to vocational training to after 3 - 4 years they have a diploma equivalent to a high school diploma has just 3/7.

Fourth, each homeroom teacher must list the students who are at risk of dropping out (having a difficult family situation, poor learning) to group up to take appropriate measures to help them. For students at risk of dropping out, teachers must diligently visit their families, chat with parents to understand students' thoughts and take timely measures to resolve them. For students with poor learning, students who stay in the classroom need to understand the cause. If due to the knowledge gap of the lower class, organize training and tutoring so that they

can keep up with their friends. For students with difficult economic conditions, it is recommended to provide support policies such as tuition exemption and reduction, enabling them to continue their study.

Fifthly, for students in remote areas, dropping out of school due to difficult travel conditions, schools far from their residence places, they will organize semi-boarding and boarding schools for children and families. At the same time, these are often the ones with difficult economic conditions, so it is necessary to mobilize individuals and organizations to sponsor scholarships, to help them with health insurance, sufficient clothes, and books to go to school.

Sixth, there should be sanctions for cases that force students to drop out. Many families are not really difficult but forced their children to leave school to work. The school should coordinate with local authorities to persistently propagate and shake the awareness of parents - students are the way to escape poverty in the most stable way. Overseas if parents do not create conditions for their children to go to school, they will be punished by law. For our country this has not been taken seriously, so the dropout rate is still at an alarming rate

"The current dropout of middle school students" is an urgent issue and is becoming a "hot" point for the whole society. So far, education is set by the Party and the State on top goals because a country with a high educational level is a new economy. For our country now, the economy is developing according to the trend of "industrialization - modernization," so it requires workers to be highly qualified and skilled. That is the goal of our economy in the new period but looking back on the fact that the dropout status of junior high school students is still high and it takes place in all provinces and cities of the country.

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